

TREND REPORT 6

QUALIFICATION PROCEDURES PUT TO THE TEST

Key takeaways

Qualification procedures (QP) in vocational education and training are pivotal for upholding quality standards and have been the subject of intense debate for some time. This can be attributed to the sometimes high failure rates, technological developments, and the fact that they are anchored in the militia system.

QP structure and success

- The QP structure varies significantly between apprenticeship occupations. As a rule, QPs cover general education, professional knowledge, the practical project, and the performance grade based on experience gained during the apprenticeship. Some professions also include partial exams in the second year of the apprenticeship.

- This analysis of QPs underscores the need to assess the quality of the practical project and professional knowledge given their significant impact on exam success across various professions.

QP failure and its consequences

- The first-time QP pass rate varies significantly based on the apprenticeship occupation, canton, and the characteristics of both the learners and companies. Nevertheless, subsequent attempts result in nearly all learners passing the QPs after sitting the final exams.
- Professions with high QP failure rates are characterised by a combination of risk factors, including a disproportionately high number of academically weaker (male) learners with a migrant background, a tendency towards a lower

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quality of training and a practical project structure that increases the likelihood of failure.

- Learners who do not pass the QPs are disproportionately more likely to be neither employed nor in training later on, and they typically earn a lower average income.

Electronic qualification procedures and artificial intelligence

- Technological advancements in electronic qualification procedures (eQPs) and artificial intelligence (AI) have the potential to impact the development, implementation and assessment of QPs, fuelling discussions on innovative examination approaches.
- The use of eQPs and AI needs to be assessed differently across different professions. It can contribute to making QPs more realistic, cost-effective and inclusive, but it also raises questions regarding the implementation of competence orientation, access to suitable hardware and software, AI misuse and data security.

The militia system of examination experts under pressure

- Examination experts (Prüfungsexpertinnen und -experten, PEXs) play a crucial role in preparing, implementing and evaluating QPs, with a significant number of PEXs engaged across Switzerland every year to assess over 70,000 learners in QPs.
- PEXs are integral to Switzerland's militia system, which is grappling with growing recruitment issues. Some professions are experiencing difficulties in recruiting enough qualified PEXs. This can jeopardise the quality of QPs and requires collaborative solutions among affiliated partners.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Qualification procedures (QP) correspond to the former final apprenticeship exams that must be taken at the end of any vocational education and training (VET) programme to obtain either the Swiss Federal VET Diploma (FVD) or the Swiss Federal VET Certificate (FVC). QPs therefore refer to all procedures used to determine whether a person possesses the competences specified in the respective VET Ordinance.¹

QPs perform a number of important functions.² They serve as performance assessments to ensure that learners have acquired the necessary professional competences and are employable. They also legitimise the differentiation and delimitation of various educational pathways, helping to ensure the quality of training and maintain training standards. Furthermore, they regulate and legitimise who gains access to professions and certain positions in the labour market and in society as a whole. To perform these functions, QPs must meet a set of quality criteria. For instance, they must be valid and measure whether learners have acquired the necessary professional competences outlined in the VET Ordinance. They should also provide reliable, error-free results that are not subjectively biased, with a reasonable overall effort for all participants and comparable conditions for all learners.

A unique aspect of QPs is that they are designed not only to assess competences typically taught in the traditional vocational school context, but also professional competences acquired in inter-company courses and especially in the workplace. Given the constant evolution of the working and professional world, QPs must be regularly reviewed and adapted to ensure they effectively fulfil their core functions.

Against this backdrop, it is possible to pinpoint four central challenges for QPs, which are currently under discussion in the world of work, the media, educational policy and research:

1. the specific structure of QPs,
2. the sometimes high failure rates,
3. the increasing digitalisation and use of artificial intelligence, which have an impact on the structure and implementation of QPs, and
4. the availability of a sufficient number of examination experts.

The specific **structure** of QPs has been the subject of intense debate since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and the temporary suspension of certain QP elements. Various professions and industries are grappling with the dilemma of choosing the right examination formats or reforming and enhancing individual QP elements and their impact on passing (or failing) the QPs. Some apprenticeships also experience high failure rates, which frequently attract significant media attention.³⁻⁵ The reasons for high **failure rates** in specific professions have not been extensively researched to date. Possible factors include differences among apprenticeships in terms of learner composition, average training quality and the structure of the QPs.

The increasing **digitalisation** of teaching methods, learning and work processes as well as developments in the field of **AI** are having a real impact on the way QPs are structured and implemented. Experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic have further accelerated this trend, leading to increased reflection on the potential of digital examination approaches and their implementation in some apprenticeships.^{6, 7} At the same time, the rapid advancement and widespread adoption of AI have posed challenges to implementing innovative and valid QPs.

The fourth challenge is linked to the fact that QPs in VET are carried out with the help of **examination experts** (Prüfungsexpertinnen und -experten, PEXs) – experienced and active professionals who volunteer part-time for this task. This means that the implementation and quality of QPs depend on the militia system, which is facing real challenges due to rising workloads and cost pressure in companies, not to mention social shifts towards individualisation. It is therefore essential to consider how the role of PEXs can be strengthened in the future to ensure they can continue to fulfil their crucial responsibilities effectively.

This trend report is intended to address each of these challenges. Chapter 2 clarifies the key concepts relating to QPs and explains the criteria for good examinations. Chapters 3 and 4 deal with various aspects of QP failure, with chapter 3 exploring the role of QP structure in the occupation-specific failure rate, while chapter 4 examines the influence of learners' individual characteristics and the quality of company-based training. Chapter 4 also addresses differences between apprenticeships and cantons and analyses whether learners who fail the QPs are affected by educational or income-related disadvantages in the years that follow. Chapter 5 looks at technological developments and discusses the potential and risks of electronic QPs and AI. Chapter 6 examines the role of PEXs in the militia system and presents considerations on how their availability can be ensured. Finally, the trend report concludes with a discussion and formulates recommendations for action.

2 QUALIFICATION PROCEDURES IN A NUTSHELL

Synopsis

- Qualification procedures (QP) typically comprise the following elements: professional knowledge, general education, practical project and a performance grade, with an optional partial exam in the second year of the apprenticeship.
- These elements are assessed through oral, written or practical examinations.
- The practical project is either standardised and assigned to all learners or individualised and tailored to the company context. In both cases, it is graded by officially appointed examination experts.
- Elements designed as mandatory pass components must be passed with a sufficient grade to pass the QPs overall and cannot be compensated by grades from other elements.
- The final exams in general education, professional knowledge and the practical project are tightly scheduled at the end of the last year of the apprenticeship. The performance grade is calculated over the entire course of the apprenticeship, with the partial exam taking place at the end of the second year. Two resits are permitted in the event of failure.
- The QP adheres to strict quality criteria to meet the required standards.

The term qualification procedures (QP) has replaced the term final apprenticeship exams. It encompasses all procedures in basic vocational education and training (VET) to determine whether learners have the competences required by the respective VET Ordinance. QPs help to ensure the quality of training, confirm the suitability of graduates for the job market and further training, and maintain established standards across various professions. The implementation of the QPs is a shared responsibility involving the canton or the cantonal QP commission, professional organisations, vocational schools and companies. For their part, learners demonstrate that they have the necessary professional competences and can apply them in their day-to-day work.⁸

Structure

QPs comprise various building blocks (see Figure 1), which are specified by the federal government in the form of guidelines. Within the framework of professional development, the professional organisations have a certain leeway in defining the QPs⁸, leading to variations in its specific structure depending on the occupation. The QP elements include **professional knowledge** and **general education**, where content from vocational school classes is examined and evaluated by teachers. Another core qualification area is the **practical project**, which tests job-related content and competences. The learners' work is assessed by at least two examination experts (PEXs) (see chapter 6), who are appointed by the cantonal office or examination board. In some professions, there are also **partial examinations** during the apprenticeship, in which PEXs test job-related content. This is usually supplemented by the **performance grade**, which is included as a preliminary score in the overall grade. It is made up of semester grades from vocational education classes and optionally includes those from inter-company courses and workplace training. The weighted average of the grades from all QP elements forms the overall QP grade.

Examination formats

The individual QP elements can be tested in different ways, with the examination formats shown in the lower part of Figure 1. Depending on the occupation, professional knowledge is tested orally, in writing or in a combination of the two. In addition to the academic performance grade, the general education element includes a written final exam along with a written special project accompanied by an oral presentation. A distinctive feature of QPs in dual-track VET is the practical project component. This is carried out either in the form of a pre-assigned examination project or individual practical project and is typically accompanied by a topical discussion. In the case of a pre-assigned examination project (PEP), the specific task is defined by the relevant professional organisation and is generally the same for all learners within a particular occupation. All learners carry out the PEP at the same time, either

Figure 1: The qualification procedure and its components

Source: Stylized illustration based on Figure 12 from the PEX handbook⁹.

centrally at a location such as a professional organisation training centre or remotely within the training company.¹⁰ The optional partial exam that takes place earlier also takes the form of a PEP.

In contrast, an individual practical project (IPP) is defined specifically for each learner and carried out in the training company as part of a company work assignment. The content is determined jointly by the supervisor and the learner and submitted to the assigned PEX team for approval. The process or product, documentation, presentation and topical discussion are evaluated by the PEXs with the involvement of the supervisor.¹⁰

Most frequently tested QP elements

The VET Ordinance for each occupation determines how the individual QP elements are structured and weighted. In most professions, QPs comprise four elements in the form of the practical project, professional knowledge, general education, and the performance grade. Other professions examine fewer or more than these four QP elements. The professional knowledge element is not part of the QPs in all professions, nor is the partial exam. A few occupations have a specific feature that serves to test additional job-specific competences.

Grade calculation and pass criteria

Individual QP elements and their grades can be weighted freely, with the exception of general education, which must count for at least 20 per cent of the overall grade. The VET Ordinance governs the calculation not only of the overall grade from the partial grades, but also of the pass criteria, which represents the minimum requirements that must be met for successful completion of the QPs. A key regulation here is which QP elements are designed as mandatory pass components.¹¹ Learners must achieve a certain grade in the mandatory pass components – or at least a grade of 4.0 – in order to pass the QPs. These cannot be compensated by other grades. In concrete terms, an unsatisfactory grade in a mandatory component results in total QP failure, even if the overall QP grade is mathematically sufficient. Mandatory pass components are therefore designed to highlight the particular importance of a given QP element for practising the occupation. In principle, all QP elements can be designed as mandatory pass components. However, this classification tends to be reserved almost always for the practical projectⁱ.

Timing

Figure 2 illustrates the timing of the QP process using the example of a four-year apprenticeship. The QPs span the entire apprenticeship period, since the **performance grade** is made up of continuously accumulated

partial grades. The optional **partial exam** in the form of a PEP takes place before the final exams at the end of the apprenticeship, towards the end of the second year for both three- and four-year FVD apprenticeships (with the exception of the cabinet maker FVD programme). Most elements, however, are examined in the final months of dual-track VET. The oral and written final exams in **professional knowledge** and **general education** take place over a few days or weeks in the spring of the final year of the apprenticeship. The **practical project**, optionally including a topical discussion, is typically submitted and assessed during the same period. The IPP, which can span up to 120 hours, usually takes longer than the PEP and begins much earlier in the dual-track VET programme. Participation in the QPs is mandatory for all learners.

They are normally registered by the cantonal authority or the examination board. All grades from the QP elements are consolidated by the cantonal examination board and/or apprenticeship authority, which determines and verifies the overall results. The results are announced and the grade reports issued in June or July. In the event of failure, all unsatisfactory elements must be retaken. Candidates retaking examinations may continue to attend the vocational school in the meantime. However, training companies are not obliged to employ the learners during this period. It is still possible to retake an examination without an apprenticeship contract. Learners who fail the QPs on their first attempt are permitted to enrol for a maximum of two resits. The resits are not intended to cause any additional work for those involved, hence they are often scheduled in the following year together with the regular examinations. Some cantons organise resits every six months.

Figure 2: QP timing with final exam on a four-year apprenticeship

Quality criteria

- QPs are considered ‘good’ if they fulfil the functions outlined in the introduction in the best possible way.² A series of criteria apply to their development, implementation and evaluation to assess their quality. This report distinguishes between five key quality criteria, which can also be found in the relevant VET literature on the subject.^{14, 15}
- **Validity: The exam measures what is to be measured and nothing else.** This means, for example, that only the competences defined in the VET Ordinance for the occupation are tested.
- **Reliability: The exam and exam results are assessed reliably and accurately, without any measurement errors.** One example of this is the uniform assessment of learners’ performance according to previously defined grading standards.
- **Objectivity: The exam and exam results are assessed objectively.** This means that the assessment of performance does not depend on the person or software carrying out the assessment.
- **Economy: The exam is uncomplicated and straightforward.** It therefore does not impose excessive demands on time, materials, financial or human resources.
- **Fairness: The exam conditions are as equal or equivalent as possible for all learners.**¹⁴ The results therefore do not lead to any systematic discrimination, for example based on ethnicity, regional origin or special educational needs.ⁱⁱⁱ

Ideally, QPs are therefore valid and measure exactly what is intended, deliver reliable and error-free results that are not subjectively biased, and involve a manageable overall workload for all parties with comparable conditions for all learners.

The quality criteria can also influence each other: reliability and objectivity, for example, are prerequisites for validity. The criteria must be balanced on a case-by-case basis, as there may be conflicting objectives, particularly with regard to the economy aspect. If the available resources are limited, it may be necessary to make compromises.

3 THE ARCHITECTURE OF QUALIFICATION PROCEDURES: QP BUILDING BLOCKS AND THEIR IMPORTANCE FOR ASSESSMENT SUCCESS

Synopsis

- The structure of the examinations is crucial to their quality and influences the success of the learners.
- An analysis of the qualification procedures (QP) in canton Bern shows that the QP elements have very different proportions of unsatisfactory grades: while over 16 per cent do not pass the professional knowledge exam, only around 1 per cent have unsatisfactory performance grades.
- The practical project represents the most common reason for failing the QPs. Although only one in twenty-five learners has an unsatisfactory grade in this area, the practical project in almost all professions represents a mandatory pass component in which learners must achieve a sufficient grade to pass the QPs.
- Learners in professions that involve an individual practical project pass QPs significantly more often overall than learners in professions with a pre-assigned examination project.
- When designing QPs in the future, it is important to consider whether the current examination practices meet the quality requirements or whether adjustments are necessary. The practical project and professional knowledge are key focal points here given their significant impact on success rates.

What is tested and why?

The structure of the QPs is the subject of intense debate during vocational training reviews and across professions. For instance, questions arise as to whether the written final exams in professional knowledge and general education are useful at all or whether the other QP modules would suffice to assess the relevant competences of the learners.¹⁷ An important consideration in the discussions around QP structure is the correlation between QP elements and exam success, particularly whether specific QP elements are linked to markedly higher failure rates. So far, there has been a lack of systematic analyses, hence this chapter is dedicated to the question of what role the individual QP elements and examination formats play in QP failure. Answers are provided by an analysis of comprehensive data on QPs in canton Bern, which is described in more detail in the ‘Data and methods’ box.

Not all QP elements feature in all professions. Figure 3 shows the number of professions (blue) and learners (green) for which a QP element is used. All professions test general education, but at 93 per cent, not quite all learners are tested in this area. This does not apply to learners who are completing the Swiss Federal Vocational Baccalaureate (FVB 1) or have a previous qualification, for example another apprenticeship qualification or general baccalaureate (Matura), and are therefore exempt from general education classes.

Figure 3: Proportion of professions and learners per tested QP element

Source: QP data for canton Bern, 2018–2023, excluding 2020 due to COVID-19; own calculations.

All but two professions test through the practical project. However, this applies to only 82 per cent of the learners, as the two major professions of commercial employee FVD and office assistant FVC evaluated practical competences differently during the period under review.

The discrepancies between professions and learners are significantly smaller when it comes to professional knowledge and the performance grade: these QP elements are tested in over 90 per cent of all professions and learners. The partial exam, which is a practical assessment of the general basic vocational competences, is only found in 24 of 220 professions. Nevertheless, as these include major professions such as commercial employee FVD, electronics engineering FVD and mechanical engineering FVD, around a quarter of all learners still take a partial exam.

QP elements and the role of mandatory pass components for success

According to Figure 4, the proportion of unsatisfactory grades in individual QP elements varies across all professions during the observation period between around 16 per cent in professional knowledge and just under one per cent in the performance grade. The proportions of unsatisfactory grades in the partial exam (3%), practical project (4%) and general education (11%) lie in between.

At over 16 per cent, the proportion of unsatisfactory grades in professional knowledge initially appears high. Nevertheless, unsatisfactory grades in this element rarely lead to failing QPs. A considerable 13 per cent of learners still pass the QPs with an unsatisfactory grade

Data and methods

The analyses in this chapter are based on administrative data from the cantonal secondary school and VET office in Bern. They include all learners who have completed a regular dual-track VET in a training company in canton Bern and have taken part in the QPs for the first time or repeatedly between 2018 and 2023. The analyses are based on a total of around 36,745 QP results.

The QP success and grades of the learners were analysed across the years 2018 to 2023. The 2020 COVID-19 year was not taken into account, as the usual final exams on professional knowledge and general education did not take place. Learners who were older than 25 at the start of their apprenticeship or who were not completing a regular dual-track VET were also excluded. Factors such as gender, nationality and occupation were taken into account in the statistics.

A more detailed description of the methods and data can be found in the online appendix on the SFUVET website: 'Trend reports OBS SFUVET'.

in professional knowledge (yellow bar). There are also 3 per cent of learners who could compensate for their unsatisfactory grade but do not pass the QPs due to further unsatisfactory grades or an unsatisfactory overall grade (orange bar). Just under 1 per cent of learners cannot compensate for the unsatisfactory grade because their professional knowledge represents a failing grade in their occupation (red bar).

Figure 4: Proportion of learners with unsatisfactory grades in the respective QP element

Source: QP data for canton Bern, 2018–2023, excluding 2020 due to COVID-19, rounded values.

At 11 per cent (bar total), the proportion of learners failing the general education element is fairly large. However, because there are no independent mandatory pass components (red part of the bar missing), 9 per cent of learners manage to compensate for unsatisfactory performance with grades from other elements (yellow bar). Only 2 per cent of learners also fail the QPs due to an unsatisfactory grade in general education (orange bar).

Unsatisfactory marks for the practical project can almost never be compensated for, as this QP element is designed as a mandatory pass component for 90 per cent of learners. This means that an unsatisfactory performance in this area almost always leads to QP failure (red bar section), even if the proportion of learners with an unsatisfactory grade in the practical project is low overall at just over 4 per cent (bar total). If the partial exam result is unsatisfactory, it must be retaken and passed in most professions by the start of the final examination period for all QP elements. This is why there are no QP failures due to a mandatory pass grade in the partial exam (no red bar section). An unsatisfactory grade can only occur in professions where passing the partial exam with a sufficient grade is not mandatory, hence the proportion of learners with unsatisfactory grades is only 3 per cent overall. In 1 per cent of cases, the unsatisfactory grade is accompanied by a QP failure (orange bar section); in 2 per cent, it can be compensated for (yellow bar section).

These results show that the grade for the practical project in its role as a mandatory pass component is often a decisive factor in whether someone passes the QPs or not. Unsatisfactory grades in professional knowledge are the second most common reason for failing the QPs. The other QP elements – general education, performance grade and partial exam – are less decisive in this respect. The next step is therefore to take a closer look at the examination formats for the practical project and the professional knowledge exam.

Varying QP success depending on the examination format

The practical project and professional knowledge that most frequently lead to failing QPs can be tested in different ways. The first step is to analyse whether there are any differences between the individual practical project (IPP) and the pre-assigned examination project (PEP). Around a third of the learners complete their practical project in the form of an IPP, and around two thirds as a PEP. The PEP is standardised, as the location,

time and tasks are the same for all learners. This enhances comparability, which should benefit certain occupations with standardised processes or products in the QPs. As the IPP is designed in collaboration with the training company, it appears to be a particularly suitable examination format in social, creative and manual professions, or when specific professional requirements, materials/infrastructure, or personnel, time or money make this necessary.¹¹ In many cases, the greater flexibility of the IPP should benefit the learners, as they are involved in determining the task, have more time to complete it, and their supervisor is involved in the assessment in addition to the two examination experts (PEXs). This all helps to represent the familiar workplace setting.

Figure 5 shows the proportion of learners with unsatisfactory grades in the PEP or IPP overall and in the eight largest professions, along with their classification as a mandatory pass component and QP success or failure. It is evident that the proportion of unsatisfactory grades is significantly higher for learners working on a PEP at just under 6 per cent than for those working on an IPP at 2 per cent. There are also major differences in this regard across occupations, with licensed electricians having notably higher rates of unsatisfactory grades in their PEP, and IT specialists in their IPP. As the practical project is normally a mandatory pass component, unsatisfactory marks in both types of examination have a decisive impact on overall QP success (red bar sections).

A closer look at the examination format is also relevant in the case of professional knowledge, as there are numerous unsatisfactory grades in this QP element. A good half of the learners in Bern are tested on their professional knowledge through both written and oral exams, just under a third are tested exclusively in written form, and around a quarter are tested in variable formats, such as written and/or oral exams combined with a performance grade. The proportion of learners with unsatisfactory grades is 17 per cent for written and oral exams, 16 per cent for written only, and 13 per cent for variable formats. It should be noted, however, that the examination formats vary by occupation, and occupations exhibit considerable differences in the composition of their learners. Considering the fact that women, learners with Swiss citizenship, and holders of the FVB 1 are more likely to pass the professional knowledge examination, the differences in the QP success rates by examination format largely disappear. The specific examination format of the professional knowledge element therefore plays a somewhat minor role in the relatively high proportion of unsatisfactory grades.

Figure 5: Proportion of learners with unsatisfactory grades in the practical project, broken down by IPP and PEP

The chart shows that in occupations with a PEP, a total of just under 6% of learners have an unsatisfactory grade, whereby this almost always leads to QP failure (red bar) for around 5% of learners because it is a mandatory pass component. In the few cases in which the PEP is not a mandatory pass component, the unsatisfactory grade is sometimes still associated with a failure (orange bar section) or can be compensated for (yellow bar section). ‘N’ denotes the number of cases in the data that were included in the analysis. Source: QP data for canton Bern, 2018–2023, excluding 2020 due to COVID-19; own calculations, rounded values.

QP structure: Focus on professional knowledge and the practical project

The structure of QPs is the subject of intense debate among all affiliated partners. On the one hand, many stakeholders advocate for a stronger focus on competence-based assessment in the QP elements and examination formats. On the other hand, the relevance and efficiency of individual elements are sometimes called into question, particularly regarding the written exams for professional knowledge and general education.

The available analyses for canton Bern indicate that learners often achieve unsatisfactory grades in the professional knowledge examinations. Scrapping the written examinations for professional knowledge could be a huge relief for many learners. But the crucial question is whether the professional knowledge required for each occupation would still be adequately tested in the QPs overall. Research results show that professional knowledge holds significant importance for learners’ future careers.¹⁸ The only scenario in which a separate

examination of this component could be considered unnecessary would be if the chosen combination of performance grades and practical project effectively evaluates the essential professional knowledge and competences in a manner that is comprehensive, valid and fair. The same applies to general education: although it may not directly contribute to professional proficiency, it still prepares learners for various aspects of life and the concept of lifelong learning. This examination is rarely responsible for QP failures. Nonetheless, dispensing with written examinations could diminish the subject’s perceived importance among learners and compromise their motivation to learn. Ideally, the written examinations should be structured to enhance the overall quality of the QPs. This is the case, for example, when they complement other examination elements in terms of content and methodology, as not all relevant knowledge and competences can be optimally tested elsewhere. This analysis cannot conclusively determine whether or to what extent this applies across professions today; this would require an occupation-specific investigation to assess how well

current exams meet the criteria for effective assessment and the contribution well-designed exams can make to each QP. Nevertheless, the high proportion of unsatisfactory grades shows that the overall quality of the professional knowledge QP element should be scrutinised more closely. It is also necessary to check whether learners are receiving the best possible training or whether vocational education classes in particular need to be improved.

It is also important to highlight the role of the practical project, which often causes many learners to fail the QPs due to its nature as a mandatory pass component. There are considerable differences between the IPP and the PEP, with the decision in favour of one over another often based on specific professional requirements. Nevertheless, the question arises as to whether the PEP might be significantly more challenging for learners

than the IPP, as it does not involve any company-specific context or the presence of a supervisor from within the company, thereby failing to reflect the familiar workplace setting. The result of a PEP therefore depends more on how well it corresponds to the learner's professional experience: for example, were the learners able to practise the task in question frequently, or did the company use the specialist terminology required for the examination? The individualised nature of the IPP, on the other hand, makes this test less comparable and objective, prompting a need to weigh up the aspects of validity, fairness and objectivity (see chapter 2) when choosing between a PEP or IPP. Similar considerations regarding the quality of the QPs should also be made when using other QP elements, as well as the examination instruments used and their complexity (multiple-choice questions, gap-fill exercises, etc.).

4 THE QUALIFICATION PROCEDURE IN FIGURES: WHO PASSES, WHO FAILS AND WHAT HAPPENS NEXT?

Synopsis

- Media reports regularly highlight that failure rates in the qualification procedure (QP) are high in individual occupations.
- On average, 6 per cent of learners do not pass the QP on their first attempt. However, most succeed after further attempts, ultimately around 99 per cent of those who take the test.
- Learners with the following characteristics have the best chances of passing the QP on their first attempt: female, Swiss citizenship, lower secondary (Sec I) level education with higher academic standards, and a training company with higher training quality.
- There are significant differences in success rates on the first QP attempt between professions. Furthermore, occupations with high failure rates lose many learners due to career exits before attempting the QP.
- Success rates on the first QP attempt vary considerably among cantons, ranging from 86 to 99 per cent. Taking exam results into account, these differences decrease to about 2 per cent.
- Learners who do not pass the QP are later disproportionately more likely to be neither employed nor in training, and they typically earn a lower average income.

In Switzerland, around 70,000 people take the final examinations of the dual-track vocational education and training (VET) programme every year. On a long-term average, around 93 per cent of candidates pass the QP on their first attempt, as shown in Figure 6. Success rates are slightly higher for two-year apprenticeships leading to a Swiss Federal VET Certificate (FVC) than for the three- and four-year apprenticeships leading to a Swiss Federal VET Diploma (FVD). These figures are fairly stable over time, with the exception of 2020, when parts of the QP could not be carried out due to COVID-19.^{iv} To delve deeper into who does not pass the QP, the analysis focuses on the educational pathways of all learners who began their dual-track VET for the first time in the summer of 2014 (entry cohort 2014; see ‘Data and meth-

Figure 6: Success rate at the first QP attempt, 2012–2022

Source: Own calculations based on data from longitudinal analyses in the education sector (LABB data) from the Federal Statistical Office (FSO).

ods’ box). The aim here is to answer the question of how the QP failure rate differs between learners with different characteristics, from companies with different training quality, and from different occupations and cantons. It is also interesting to see whether learners who do not pass the QP or do not pass it at the first attempt end up on different educational and career pathways later on. Of the learners who started their apprenticeship in 2014, around 90 per cent sat their final examinations within five years. Of these, 94 per cent passed the QP on their first attempt, as illustrated in Figure 7. Ninety per cent of learners who did not pass on their first attempt took the opportunity to retake the failed qualification areas. After resitting once or twice, 99 per cent of learners who had taken the final examinations for the first time by 2019 passed the QP (dark and light green). QP success differs slightly between different groups of learners, as shown in Figure 7. Women, learners with Swiss citizenship and learners who attended a school at lower secondary level (Sec I) with higher academic standards have a slightly higher success rate at the first QP attempt and a slightly higher overall success rate than men, learners without Swiss citizenship and learners who attended school at lower secondary level with more basic academic standards. Learners who had their apprenticeship contract terminated (PACT) during their training period have a lower chance of passing the QP on their first attempt and overall than learners who did not have their contract terminated. These differences

Figure 7: Training pathway according to learner characteristics

Note: The diagram shows the training pathways of learners in the 2014 entry cohort who took the final examinations by 2019 (N=48,544). Source: Own calculations based on FSO LABB data.

between different learner groups remain when multi-variate analyses (see ‘Data and methods’ box) are used to take into account all the characteristics shown in the figure along with other characteristics, such as the requirements profile of the apprenticeship, the standardisation level of the QP, the geographical region and the professional field.^v

The importance of company training quality

Training companies play a central role in the training and support of learners involved in dual-track VET. Ideally, they teach their learners all the competences listed in the VET Ordinance and support them throughout their training. Training quality includes aspects such as a suitable learning environment and appropriate conditions, as well as characteristics of the training process, such as adequate organisation of work tasks and the quality of supervision and support for learners. Furthermore, training quality has an impact on whether learners acquire the professional competences required to pass the QP.^{21, 22}

The results of these analyses show that learners who receive more varied learning tasks in their companies and can work independently by finding their own solutions tend to pass the QP slightly more often than learners in companies where this is less common. Also, learners in large companies, which typically have more resources for training, tend to be more successful in the QP compared to those in small and medium-sized

Data and methods

The analyses in this chapter are based on the longitudinal data from the Federal Statistical Office’s modernised educational statistics (LABB data). The primary focus is on the educational pathways of learners who entered dual-track VET for the first time in the summer of 2014 and took the QP by 2019 (N = 48,544). Interest then shifts to the further educational and career pathways of learners with and without QP failures from the cohort of learners who took the QP in dual-track VET for the first time in 2018 and have no earlier VET qualification (N = 53,908). For specific analyses on the role of training companies, a link is also made with the data from the fourth cost-benefit survey of VET from the perspective of companies.²⁰ A more detailed description of the methods and data can be found in the online appendix on the SFUVET website: ‘Trend reports OBS SFUVET’. Possible factors influencing QP success are first presented descriptively in graphical form and subsequently analysed using multivariate regression analyses. These can be used to determine whether a particular characteristic, such as a person’s social background, has a positive or negative correlation with QP success when other characteristics are held constant.

companies.^{23,24} Consequently, differences between training companies mean that even learners from the same professions and with similar personal characteristics have unequal chances of success in the QP. This can be critically evaluated in terms of the fairness of the final exams, hence the question arises of how to ensure that all training companies can provide high-quality training. The necessary framework conditions for high-quality training include ensuring that those responsible for VET in all companies have sufficient time available to teach their learners and that they are relieved of their other duties.²⁴ Particularly in small and medium-sized companies, those responsible for VET are caught between balancing the demands of production with training requirements.^{24, 25}

Success rate varies significantly across occupations

In certain occupations, significantly fewer learners pass the QP on their first attempt than the average for all occupations, as shown in Figure 8. The overall success rate after resits is also lower than average in most of these professions. These substantial differences in QP success among professions raise the question of

whether all learners have equal opportunities to pass the QP regardless of their chosen occupation. In addition, failures are usually very stressful for the learners affected.

Furthermore, high failure rates pose a challenge for the professions and industries themselves. They jeopardise the professional image and can exacerbate shortages of skilled workers, because in some professions with high failure rates, many learners drop out before completing their training. To illustrate this, Figure 9 combines the success rate in the QP (vertical axis) with the proportion of learners who leave the occupation before attempting the QP and choose a different career path (horizontal axis). The dashed lines represent the average for both dimensions across all professions, dividing the graph into four quadrants.

Many apprenticeships can be found in the top left quadrant. In these professions, the QP success rate on the first attempt is above average, and only relatively few learners leave the occupation before attempting the QP. Similarly, the lower right quadrant also contains many apprenticeships. These are characterised by a relatively low success rate on the first QP attempt, plus a higher than average number of young people who leave their originally chosen occupation before attempting the QP. The upper right quadrant includes several occupations

Figure 8: Apprenticeships with the lowest QP success rates on first attempt

The chart shows the ten occupations with the lowest success rates compared to the average for all professions (N > 50 learners at entry). It also indicates the success rate on the first QP attempt for learners who started in their respective apprenticeship in 2014 and took the QP in that occupation. In some of the professions shown, the success rate on the first attempt fluctuates slightly from year to year or has improved slightly over time. However, the success rate in 2022 still remained significantly below average across all professions shown. Source: Own calculations based on FSO LABB data.

with very high success rates on the first attempt (e.g. retail professional FVD), but also sees a higher than average number of learners leaving the occupation before the QP. In the lower left quadrant, there are some apprenticeships (e.g. electrical installation designer FVD) that have a below-average success rate on the first attempt, with relatively few career changes. The red line indicates a correlation between QP failure and career exits. Professions in the lower right quadrant lose a significant portion of their learners during training due to career changes and have low success rates among the remaining learners on the first QP attempt. These professions are therefore under double the strain. There are many possible reasons for these professional differences. To better understand how professions with low success rates and high reorientation rates (bottom right in Figure 9) differ from those with high success rates and low reorientation rates (top left), the two groups are compared in Table 1 based on various characteristics. The analyses suggest that risk factors tend to accumulate in certain professions (see Figure 10). Firstly, differences are evident between the two groups in the training and demographic characteristics of the

learners. Occupations with a low first-time pass rate in the QP and frequent reorientations, have a higher proportion of learners who attended a lower secondary (Sec I) school with basic academic standards, repeated a year of apprenticeship, or had their apprenticeship contract terminated than occupations with a high first-time pass rate in the QP and less frequent reorientations. These professions also have a significantly higher proportion of male learners and more learners without Swiss citizenship.

Secondly, the two groups differ in terms of occupation-specific factors. Occupations with low success rates on the first QP attempt and several reorientations typically have lower academic requirements, which means they train more learners who are not particularly strong academically. It is also noteworthy that this group of occupations tends to favour the PEP practical project format, whereas the choice varies significantly in the comparison group. Chapter 3 highlighted that the risk of QP failure is higher in professions using PEP compared to those using IPP.

Thirdly, Table 1 illustrates that the average training quality in professions with high QP failure and reorientation

Figure 9: Success rate on – and career exits before – the first QP attempt

Note: Only occupations with more than 50 candidates at the start of the programme (2014) are shown (N = 94). Those who left their chosen occupation without attempting the QP either completed the QP in a different occupation, successfully completed general or full-time training, exited the education system without a qualification, or were still in training in 2019. The career exits before the first QP attempt shown on the horizontal axis are therefore not identical to the PACT rate, as the latter only sometimes involves a change of occupation. The chart also shows the results for learners who started in their respective apprenticeship in 2014 and took the QP in that occupation. Source: Own calculations based on FSO LABB data.

Table 1: Differences between professional groups in terms of average characteristics

Professional characteristic	Professional group	
	High success & low reorientation rate	Low success & high reorientation rate
Sec I level with basic academic standards*	38 %	68 %
Resit rate before QP attempt	3 %	7 %
Apprenticeship contract termination rate	18 %	34 %
Proportion of men	55 %	87 %
No CH citizenship	17 %	30 %
Average requirement level**	3,27	1,48
IPP or PEP	Varied	Predominantly PEP
Average in-house training quality***	Slightly above average	Significantly below average

* In cantons with different types of Sec I schools, the Sec I level with basic academic standards (i.e. without enhanced standards) includes those with general or basic academic standards, such as Sec A (e.g. BS, BL, not ZH), Sec B (e.g. ZH, SO), Sec C (e.g. ZH) and Realschule (e.g. AG, BE, FR, SG).

** Requirement level: Scale from 1–6 with 6 being highest academic requirement level.

*** Training quality: Index of various aspects of training quality; see online appendix on the SFUVET website: ‘Trend reports OBS SFUVET’.

rates is lower compared to the comparison group. It is also possible that there are differences between the occupations in the way they approach weaker learners. For instance, in some professions, learners who have not yet acquired the necessary competences might systematically be discouraged from taking the QP, whereas in other professions, they may proceed to take the final exams. This could contribute to the differences observed across the professions.

In summary, the findings in Table 1 indicate that in apprenticeships with high failure and reorientation rates, several risk factors tend to accumulate (see Figure 10). For instance, academically weaker learners, often from non-native language backgrounds with less support, frequently find themselves in companies where the training quality is below average. Moreover, these learners often have to complete the PEP practical project format, which can pose an additional hurdle for passing the QP according to the findings in chapter 3. It is plausible to assume that high QP failure and reorientation rates are a consequence of the fact that certain occupations are characterised by an above-average number of these risk factors. However, the potential interplay of these factors has not been investigated in enough detail and requires further research. A number of professional organisations have recently taken measures to increase the QP success rate in their respective fields. Suissetec, for example, is set to introduce nationwide training coaches from 2024, who will closely support learners and companies in the building technology sector with the aim of enhancing training quality in the industry and thereby reducing reorientations, premature apprenticeship contract termination (PACT), and QP failures.²⁶ HotellerieSuisse also aims to improve training quality in the hospitality industry by visiting training companies and supporting vocational trainers.²⁷ It is commendable to see companies taking positive initiatives like these, which focus on improving training quality or supporting learners.

Major differences between cantons in terms of first-time QP success

There are major differences between the cantons in terms of first-time QP pass rates, as shown in Figure 11. Learners from the central and eastern Switzerland regions pass the QP on their first attempt most frequently, while those from the Lake Geneva region and Ticino do so least often. For instance, nearly one in seven learners in Ticino do not pass the QP on their first attempt, whereas in Obwalden, this figure is only about one in a

Figure 10: Possible risk factors for QP failure

hundred. If resits are taken into account, the success rates between cantons differ by at most two percentage points, as nearly all learners pass the QP after resits in all cantons.

There has been only limited investigation into the reasons for the cantonal differences in initial QP success to date. First and foremost, the research suggests that differences in education system opportunities between cantons and the resulting varied composition of learners may be a contributing factor.^{28,29} In German-speaking cantons, where success rates tend to be higher, a significantly larger proportion of learners undertake dual-track VET compared to Romandy or Ticino, where learners often only opt for dual-track VET if they fail to enter or successfully complete their general education programmes.^{19,30} This situation could make it harder for businesses to find suitable learners, because fewer young people are interested in dual-track VET or choose them only as a last resort.^{19,30} Furthermore, a poor fit between the occupation's requirements and young people's aspirations can impact satisfaction with the training, learning progress and ultimately motivation to complete the apprenticeship.³¹

Secondly, the literature suggests that cantonal differences in the implementation of the curricula for vocational schools and the VET Ordinances could lead to differences in competences between learners and, as a result, to different success rates.³³

Thirdly, with regard to cantonal differences, the litera-

ture also notes that there are differences between small and large cantons in the relationship between examination experts (PEXs) and companies, in that this is much closer and more personal in small cantons.³³ If PEXs (have to) repeatedly go into the same companies due to the smaller volume of candidates in small cantons, this could lead to learners in these cantons having an advantage, since those responsible for VET may become more familiar with which examination content is being tested particularly frequently. Finally, differences in training conditions – and consequently success rates between cantons – could arise because the apprenticeship authority in some cantons is in a position to offer closer supervision to companies compared to others, due to significant variations in workload among cantonal professional inspectors.³⁴

QP failure impacts mid-term labour market and training prospects

To examine the potential consequences of QP failures, the following section compares the employment and educational situations of learners who passed the QP first time, after a resit, or not at all. The analysis compares the situation one year and three years after the last QP attempt. The results depicted in Figure 12 show that those who only passed the QP after a resit were less likely to still be in training or education one year after completion than those who passed the QP first time.

Figure 11: QP success of learners by canton of vocational school

Note: The success per canton was calculated based on the canton in which the learners attend the vocational school. As there is no vocational school in the canton of Appenzell Innerrhoden and the learners attend schools outside the canton, no results can be presented for this canton. Nearly all learners in Obwalden passed the QP. However, the relatively low number of learners in this canton causes the results to fluctuate from year to year. The chart indicates the success rate of learners who started their apprenticeship in 2014 and took the QP by 2019. Source: Own calculations based on FSO LABB data.

These differences also apply when considering the apprenticeship occupation and various individual characteristics. It is not possible to say from the available data whether the lower level of training or education activity is related to the negative experience of ‘failure’ or whether it stems from differences in performance and aptitude for further training or education.

Furthermore, it is notable that around a third of those who did not successfully complete the QP were not in education, employment or training (NEET) one year and three years after their last QP attempt (red bars). The remaining two thirds were either employed or still in training, with most of the latter group continuing their VET. Some of these people are therefore likely to go

Figure 12: Status of individuals one year and three years after the last QP attempt, by result on the first QP attempt

The chart shows the pathways of people who started their QP in dual-track VET for the first time in 2018. Source: Own calculations based on FSO LABB data (N = 58,149).

The chart shows that 67 per cent of those who passed the QP first time in 2018 were in employment one year after graduation, 15 per cent were in training at Sec II level, 3 per cent were in education at tertiary level, 1 per cent were in another form of training, and 14 per cent were not in education, employment or training (NEET).

on to obtain an upper secondary school (Sec II) leaving certificate or have already done so. A lack of a Sec II leaving certificate can impact future earnings, as shown in Figure 13. After three years, the average monthly income of people who did not success-

fully complete the QP was around CHF 800 lower than that of people who successfully completed the QP first time or after a resit. Whether the QP was passed on the first attempt or after a resit had little bearing on income during the first three years after completion.

Figure 13: Development of the average monthly salary of employees who took the QP for the first time in 2018 (excluding people in training), by QP result

The chart shows the average non-standardised, inflation-adjusted monthly gross income in six-month increments based on the QP pathway. This means that the actual (inflation-adjusted) income is recorded for all employees who are not in training, regardless of the level of workload. Source: Own calculations based on FSO LABB data (N = 35,894).

5 NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN QUALIFICATION PROCEDURES: DIGITAL TESTING AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Synopsis

- Electronic qualification procedures (eQP) and artificial intelligence (AI) are playing an increasingly important role in QPs, as digital tools are being used more and more in the education and training as well as everyday work of many professions.
- Technological advancements can help to make QPs more realistic, cost-effective and inclusive. However, there are also risks to consider, for example with regard to access to suitable hardware and software, data security and the misuse of AI.
- The integration of new technologies into QPs is particularly important for occupations that frequently use digital tools on a daily basis. This should be reflected in the competences-based testing element of QPs.
- The use of new technologies should not be an end in itself but should be specifically tailored to the individual professions and QP components.
- The rapid development of AI is increasing the need for further education and training for teachers and examination experts (PEXs), as well as the need to share best practices.

The importance of new technologies for QPs

Ever since the COVID-19 pandemic, there has been a real shift in the use of digital tools for examinations, as their advantages were clearly acknowledged in the context of social distancing.^{6,7} Another technological breakthrough came with the introduction of AI-based chatbots and similar programs starting at the end of 2022. These new technological possibilities are widely discussed in practice, and (initial) experiences are currently being gathered in the context of examination procedures.³⁵ There is often a convergence between the use of digital tools in everyday work, education and training, and examination settings. For example, learners now frequently use their own laptops, tablets or smartphones – as well as AI programs – in their work, education and training, allowing them to acquire new

competences that need to be appropriately considered in (digital) examination situations.³⁶ Nevertheless, significant differences are emerging between professions, as the importance of digital tools in work and learning processes varies from one to the next.

Electronic QPs: Testing with digital tools

Technological developments in the workplace and in education are bringing about changes in QPs. There is increasing discussion in VET about eQP, primarily focusing on the digitalisation of the examinations required for certification. This notably includes conducting written professional knowledge exams in (partially) digital formats.^{37,38} There are also already several occupations for which practical examinations – or at least parts thereof, such as email and invoice creation and appointment scheduling – are conducted digitally. In a broader sense, the term eQP also encompasses handling digital exam management, creating and maintaining a digital pool of tasks, (pre-)evaluating and archiving exams, and training examination experts (PEXs) for the new procedures. Research on e-assessment – i.e. testing with digital tools – has been ongoing for quite some time.^{39–41} However, within the Swiss VET system, the evidence base for eQPs primarily consists of field reports and evaluations rather than comprehensive scientific studies.^{42,43}

This analysis shows that professional organisations are currently at different stages with regard to the introduction of eQPs. Some professional organisations do not (yet) see a need for eQPs, while others – such as IGKG Schweiz – are in the exploratory and implementation phase. Then there are professional organisations, including Swissmem, that have reached a point where they are (only) making adjustments after a long introductory period. Some professional organisations have been integrating digital elements into their practical final exams for a long time, such as VSSM (Association of Swiss Master Carpenters and Furniture Manufacturers) and Plavenir. Both use computer-aided design (CAD) software in final exams, where learners must create and edit precise drawings and models on the computer.

A number of professional organisations recognise the significant untapped potential of eQPs in VET.⁴²

Overall, the current state of digitalisation in final exams presents a diverse picture, which is partly because not every occupation requires extensive use of technology. Professional organisations that already make extensive use of digital technologies in their everyday work have generally been more inclined towards adopting eQPs. The diversity in eQP implementation can also be attributed to the fact that professional organisations are currently proceeding in this domain without an overarching coordination by federal and cantonal authorities.³⁵

Artificial intelligence in QPs: Fresh perspectives on examination culture?

AI is a pivotal foundational technology in the context of digitalisation.^{44,45} Since the introduction of the ChatGPT chatbot in November 2022,⁴⁶ there has been intensive discussion about the impact of generative AI on examinations and QPs – i.e. AI programs that can create content autonomously. ChatGPT not only facilitates online research, but can also write specific types of text such as emails, business letters or entire theses, condense and translate texts, develop and answer exam questions, solve arithmetic problems, generate simple programming code and plenty more besides.⁴⁷ An exam-

Data and methods

The findings in this chapter are based on the following data sources:

360-degree interviews: In the period between autumn 2023 and spring 2024, 26 representatives of various relevant stakeholder groups were interviewed. Information from interviews is cited in the same way as information from text sources (i.e. a number refers to the relevant reference in the bibliography).

Media analysis: A qualitative analysis of 203 media articles was carried out between December 2022 and September 2023.

The findings are also based on analyses of policy documents and websites of relevant stakeholders, as well as on the existing but limited academic literature.

A more detailed description of the methods and data can be found in the online appendix on the SFUVET website: 'Trend reports OBS SFUVET'.

ple of an application for ChatGPT is shown in Figure 14 for the question, 'What are the advantages and disadvantages of digital examination procedures?'. This example notably illustrates that it is becoming more and more difficult for teachers to distinguish AI texts from self-written work.⁴⁸ Generally speaking, QPs in VET are particularly affected by AI developments, as the extent to which AI is now used in working, education and training practices should also now be reflected in competence-based QPs.

The term 'AI' generally refers to systems that exhibit intelligent behaviour by analysing their environment and taking action to achieve certain goals with a certain degree of autonomy.⁴⁹ Due to the present pace and rapid development of AI, there is currently hardly any targeted research on its impact on VET QPs in Switzerland. At the time of collating this data, professional organisations had different perspectives and approaches to AI in QPs.³⁵ Some professional organisations are very open to AI but operate without their own AI policy and are partially awaiting the introduction of framework guidelines or guidance from public authorities. Other professional organisations advocate that basic competences should be acquired without AI and assessed in examinations, but that a broad use of AI should then be possible to align more closely with the realities of the workplace. Another group of professional organisations emphasises the need to strengthen a company-specific approach during education and training and, by extension, also in QPs,³⁵ as tasks tailored to specific company contexts are more difficult to answer directly using AI. At the same time, these professional organisations want to actively offer training on the use of AI, with a focus on acquiring new reading and writing competences for interacting with AI programs. This includes aspects such as prompting, which involves engaging in dialogue with digital assistants. It is also important to ensure learners adopt a critical approach to AI,⁵⁰ as the chatbots can sometimes 'hallucinate', resulting in the output containing both logical and factual errors.

Potential of eQPs and AI: Opportunities for restructuring QPs

Stronger focus on competence-based assessment

New technologies are offering huge potential for the development of more true-to-life examinations that meet the requirements for a stronger focus on competence-based assessment⁵¹ as far as possible, thereby optimising the validity of the QPs.⁵² As noted by Deutscher et al.,⁵³ innovations in VET occurring within

Figure 14: ChatGPT's answer to the question: 'What are the advantages and disadvantages of digital examination procedures?'

Advantages of digital examination procedures

1. **Flexibility:** Examinations can be taken anywhere and at any time.
2. **Efficiency:** Faster evaluation and simpler administration.
3. **Environmental friendliness:** Reduced paper consumption.
4. **Cost reductions:** Less expenditure on logistics and personnel.
5. **Versatile formats:** Use of interactive and multimedia examination formats.

Disadvantages of digital examination procedures

1. **Technical problems:** Hardware/software requirements and potential for technical breakdowns.
2. **Data protection:** Protection of sensitive data and prevention of fraud.
3. **Equal opportunities:** Unequal access to technology and the internet.
4. **Training requirements:** Need for familiarisation and technical support.
5. **Acceptance:** Reservations and uncertainty about digital examinations.

Note: Original answer generated in German by ChatGPT 4.0 on 21/05/2024. As the original response was much longer, ChatGPT was asked to provide the abridged version reproduced here. Layout inspired by the ChatGPT layout.

the framework of digitalisation in schools and companies are ultimately at risk of failing if they are not also reflected in the examination system. The focus on competence-based assessment should therefore be consistently taken into account from the outset when developing digital elements in the QPs. Examination software is particularly interesting if it can be used to create authentic professional situations that facilitate the practical application of knowledge and skills.⁵⁴ The appeal is enhanced further if complex, risky and costly work situations that can only rarely be practised in reality but are nevertheless important can be simulated virtually using AI and integrated into examination situations.⁵² When preparing for exams, practising professional competences using virtual reality has been shown to improve learners' QPs results.⁵³ This is where eQPs and AI complement each other – for example, when AI programs are used to digitally replicate workplace situations in the form of videos or images.

Increased efficiency in QPs

Digital tools also offer further potential for enhancing resource efficiency. Although there is still no comprehensive evidence on the extent to which the introduction of eQPs and AI will result in direct cost savings, it seems plausible that existing resources will be used in a more targeted manner where they contribute

to improving QP quality – for example, for the individual adaptation and optimisation of examinations for learners with special needs.⁵⁵ Nevertheless, increases in efficiency – for example, through multiple-choice questions and automated evaluations – become problematic if the use of new technologies leads to a shift away from competence testing in favour of straight knowledge tests.⁵⁶ Taking this risk into account, three avenues for enhancing efficiency in the development, implementation and evaluation of QPs can be identified. Firstly, in the area of **exam development**, AI can support the content creators with developing exam tasks. This includes creating assignments and professional situations for the written exams with the help of AI tools, thereby reducing the amount of writing work for the content creators. Secondly, the use of AI enhances efficiency in terms of QP **implementation**, as the tests no longer have to be printed out and physically transported. It is also possible to create individualised question sets, especially for digital task formats such as single- or multiple-choice responses, matching tasks, sequences, or gap-fill exercises, which are in the lower to medium level of difficulty.^{55, 57} Thirdly, digital examination formats allow individualised, detailed feedback to be generated in real time for certain task types during the **evaluation** phase.⁵⁸ This not only meets the desire of many learners to receive feedback on their performance

as quickly as possible, but also reduces the assessment effort.⁵⁹

Digital tools therefore have the potential to support or relieve teachers and PEXs. For example, illegible handwriting no longer needs to be deciphered, correction notes can be standardised and point scores can be automatically totalled.⁶⁰ The automatically generated assessment, on the other hand, still needs to be checked and supplemented if necessary. Also, cognitively demanding and more complex examination tasks cannot yet be assessed automatically, or else only to a limited extent. This presents a middle ground, where less cognitively challenging questions are pre-assessed automatically, leaving all others to be assessed directly by those responsible.

Strengthening inclusion

The use of digital technologies also holds potential for more equal opportunities. Inclusion in QPs can be improved, for example, by integrating better measures for compensating for disadvantages through digital examination software, such as enlarged fonts and new options for reading aloud and listening.⁵⁵ However, this requires targeted promotion of digital participation for disabled people – that is, with regard to their individual technical skills – beyond simply providing access to the relevant technology.⁶⁴

Challenges surrounding eQPs and AI

Access to – and use of – suitable hardware and software

The successful implementation of examinations using digital tools requires adequate hardware and software that not only facilitate reliable measurement of the competences and knowledge required in an occupation, but also make it possible to integrate practical tasks and case studies. It is also essential for learners to try out the relevant hardware and software as part of their education and training. In terms of reliability, it makes sense to anticipate technical complications in the hardware and software that may arise during the examination and provide appropriate solutions – especially when learners use their own devices for the QPs, as in the case of the professional organisation ICT-Berufsbildung Schweiz, which trialled the implementation of online examinations on candidates' personal IT devices.⁶¹ Ensuring data protection and legal compliance in handling sensitive information in the digital sphere is paramount, necessitating contemporary and transparent regulations to foster trust among all stakeholders.

With regard to the hardware and software available to learners – and thus the level of digitalisation – questions of fairness understandably arise. This notably concerns access to AI programs in working as well as education and training practices and the question of whether or to whom the latest paid version of a specific AI program is available.^{35, 62} For policymakers, this raises the question of financing or subsidising the necessary hardware and software for all learners.

Increased need for further training, open dialogue and guidance

In light of the currently different levels of knowledge, experience, perceptions and perspectives on all of these topics, there is a clear need for further education and training⁵² for teachers, vocational trainers and PEXs. To ensure that interested professional organisations can keep pace with technological advancements and benefit from the advantages of eQPs and AI despite limited resources, further education and training opportunities should be tailored to the specific needs of each profession. Another crucial component is the ability to facilitate structured exchanges of experiences and best practices. At the time of collecting data for this report, very few federal or cantonal recommendations on the topics of eQPs and AI were available to guide VET practitioners.³⁵ Other countries, such as Australia, have had specific guidelines and frameworks for e-assessments in place for some time, aimed at ensuring the quality and consistency of digital testing in VET. These e-assessment guidelines for VET contain many criteria and standards for the provision of the digital infrastructure. They also contain specific technical requirements for the development of examination tasks and the corresponding cooperation between private and public stakeholders, for the security of electronic testing, the evaluation of results, and the use and management of feedback.⁶³

Prevention of AI misuse

If AI is capable of directly answering certain questions, this poses a risk to the validity of the QPs. Attempting to prevent the use of AI through technical restrictions is challenging, since it has already been integrated into the workplace in the form of chatbots, translation tools, and language correction aids,⁶⁴ but also because AI technology is making such rapid progress. Excluding AI completely would require extensive ongoing efforts. As such, when designing a realistic examination situation where learners demonstrate their competences in a practical scenario within a (simulated) work context, excluding commonly used AI programs can be problematic in terms of both content and technology.

An alternative option is to adapt QPs as far as possible to prevent falsification of examination results despite the possible use of AI. There is also talk about reweighting certain QP modules, with one approach involving placing greater emphasis on practical projects and oral examinations,⁶⁵ as AI programs are typically limited in their ability to extend beyond the desired framework in these areas. Another strategy is to adapt questions in such a way that they go beyond querying generally available knowledge and require largely independent answers. Questions should ideally be formulated in such a way that answering them correctly assumes an understanding of the corresponding core concept, which includes formulating multi-level, context-specific and company-related questions.⁶⁶ The more questions align with this type, the more challenging it becomes to answer them directly with an AI program, as it lacks the corresponding context-specific data. At the same time, these types of questions usually fulfil the requirements of competence-based assessment due to their practical focus.

Prospects for QP digitisation

The developments in AI and eQPs are currently sparking intense discussions about the status and prospects of QPs. These new technologies are changing and expanding the possibilities of examination structure and have the potential to overhaul the entire culture of professional examination as we know it.⁶⁷ It is therefore advisable to take a comprehensive view of the effects of AI and eQPs on QPs, providing both appropriate guidance to VET practices and sufficient flexibility in the way they are implemented.

6 SHIFTING DYNAMICS IN THE MILITIA SYSTEM: THE FUTURE OF EXAMINATION EXPERTS IN QUALIFICATION PROCEDURES

Synopsis

- Trained examination experts (PEXs) ensure seamless preparation, implementation and assessment of the qualification procedures (QP) in secondary employment capacity. This involvement of experts from the world of work guarantees that the QPs are practically relevant and aligned with the current labour market.
- Volunteer work under the Swiss militia system is coming under increasing pressure, which is also impacting VET. Professional organisations are reporting an (acute) shortage of suitable PEXs in some fields.
- To ensure that sufficient PEXs are available in future, companies and young professionals can be made more aware of militia work through targeted association efforts.
- To make the role of PEXs in the militia system more appealing, considerations should include better recognition and support for their work, targeted further education and training opportunities, and streamlining of examination processes.

PEXs as key roleholders in QPs

PEXs represent a central component of QPs and are recognised as a hallmark of quality within the Swiss VET system due to their important role in connecting QPs with the professional world.⁶⁸ Nevertheless, some professional organisations are experiencing an increasing shortage of new PEXs coming through. This trend aligns with the more general societal tendency of fewer volunteers willing to engage in tasks organised within the militia system. Given the high demand for skilled PEXs, this is a potentially damaging development for VET, as a significant number of PEXs are required every year to assess over 70,000 learners. If there are not enough trained PEXs available, this raises concerns with regard to upholding quality standards for final exams (see chapter 2).

The tasks of PEXs are diverse.⁶⁹ They are mainly involved in the QP element of practical projects, and in some cas-

es also in the partial exam and professional knowledge exam. Depending on the organisation and methodology of the examination, they prepare their own questions and create the corresponding assessment criteria. In the case of individual practical projects, they review proposals for tasks and visit learners in the workplace as expert advisors. They also assess the practical project, take part in topical discussions, and document the progress and results of the examination. PEXs act as official representatives of the respective cantonal administration and must ensure that they document and evaluate objectively and fairly according to the quality criteria of good examinations. In this process, they collaborate with other involved PEXs and the cantonal chief examiner, who assembles and leads the PEX team and holds overall responsibility.⁹ Since the practical project is classified as a mandatory pass component in most professions and learners must therefore achieve a sufficient grade to pass the QPs, PEXs play a significant role in determining whether and how apprenticeship graduates enter the labour market as qualified professionals. PEXs are recruited by the professional organisations or chief examiner and appointed by the cantons.⁷⁰ If PEXs carry out their work outside of regular working hours, they are financially compensated in accordance with cantonal guidelines. This compensation is not dependent on any particular industry or occupation and is usually not comparable with normal wages. If PEXs are released from their regular duties by their employer to perform this role, the company usually receives the corresponding compensation for their time. Even so, the level of compensation is not sufficient in many sectors and professions to offset the wage costs incurred during the time off. In both cases, the compensation is provided in the spirit of the militia concept and is not intended as a salary or equivalent salary replacement. Switzerland's militia system is based on elective participation in public duties and offices, either as a secondary employment or as a volunteer, and enjoys a long and well-respected tradition throughout the country.⁷¹ Nevertheless, economic and social changes are placing real pressure on this system,⁷²⁻⁷⁴ which is consequently also being felt by the PEXs.

Shifting dynamics in the militia system

Public discourse is highlighting a diminishing interest in signing up for militia positions,⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷ with the main reasons cited for this trend including greater demands on employees and growing economic pressures on companies.⁷⁸ This is making it difficult for employees and employers alike to allocate the necessary resources to militia-related activities. Further factors impacting the militia system include the individualisation of society and demographic change. As society becomes more individualised, younger people in particular tend to show less interest in militia activities, as they prefer to focus their time and resources on personal rather than communal activities.⁷⁷ The ageing population also poses a potential problem. Older generations are currently more involved in militia work than their younger counterparts, meaning that the available pool of militia members is shrinking faster than it can be replenished.⁷⁹ Bureaucracy is yet another factor complicating militia work, for example due to increasingly complex official requirements. The partly growing administrative workload means that militia roles are now associated with a higher level of administrative responsibilities – and unappealing ones at that.⁷⁷ These additional requirements can lead to a lower willingness to get involved. The professionalisation process can also fundamentally undermine militia activities. This notably happens when these

Data and methods

The findings in this chapter are based on two main data sources:

360-degree interviews: In the period between autumn 2023 and spring 2024, 26 representatives of various relevant stakeholder groups were interviewed. Information from interviews is cited in the same way as information from text sources (i. e. a number refers to the relevant reference in the bibliography).

Media analysis: A qualitative analysis of 203 media articles was carried out between December 2022 and September 2023.

The findings are also based on analyses of policy documents and websites of relevant stakeholders, as well as on the existing but limited academic literature.

A more detailed description of the methods and data can be found in the online appendix on the SFUVET website: 'Trend reports OBS SFUVET'.

side jobs become full-time roles to meet higher quality requirements and handle increasing complexity in many areas of work. Overall, these developments and associated challenges are making it increasingly difficult within the militia system to recruit and retain sufficient qualified and committed individuals.

The challenges mentioned are also reflected in the militia work of the PEXs, particularly with regard to PEX recruitment, increasing demands on PEXs, motivation for PEX work and a shortage of PEXs, although these areas overlap to some extent.

Challenges for the work of PEXs within the militia system

PEX recruitment and increasing demands on PEXs

The professional organisations and cantons are continuously tasked with recruiting new PEXs to carry out QPs. As a general rule, the professional organisations or cantonal chief examiners recommend potential PEXs to the cantons.⁹ Communication channels such as newsletters, websites, examination/professional platforms, flyers, and professional/industry events are used to find suitable candidates, while also leveraging personal networks. However, the majority of the professional organisations surveyed lack standardised – and therefore effective – recruitment procedures for PEX trainees.³⁵ Some professional organisations are pursuing innovative approaches to solve the issue of recruiting new PEXs in the long term. VSSM, for example, inspires young professionals at regional and national level early on by involving former participants in carpentry competitions in evaluation tasks. If they are interested and suitable, these young carpenters can later be recruited for PEX tasks and developed as new PEXs. This successful recruitment approach could therefore be of interest to other sectors.

The requirements for PEXs are high. They are expected to be professionally qualified in their field, ideally with several years of experience in training learners within their company, and with the necessary social and personal competences to deal with learners in the examination situation.^{vi} To prepare for their role, they are required to complete both a basic course and an occupation-specific course, which also covers the specific requirements of the QPs.⁹ Demands on PEXs have also tended to increase in recent years as a result of bureaucratisation and professionalisation. This can notably be seen in the fact that PEXs have to deal with a significant rise in requests for accommodations and an increasing numbers of appeals related to the QPs.⁸⁰

Motivation for PEX work: Are the various incentives no longer enough?

A range of incentives at individual, company and systemic level can help to motivate people to take on this side job and attract enough qualified professionals to perform PEX tasks.

Firstly, a number of incentives are offered at an **individual level**. The role of a PEX contributes to personal development and facilitates the development of new competences. Working as a PEX means always being informed about the latest professional developments and requirements, and it can also open up new career prospects. According to professional organisations, there are sectors in which being a PEX represents a major step in career advancement.³⁵ For example, working as a PEX offers an excellent opportunity to expand professional networks, which can also be advantageous in other areas of professional life. Also, some professional organisations remunerate their PEXs financially in addition to the cantonal compensation to increase the appeal of their activities. In general, however, many VET stakeholders believe that motivation for PEX work should not be primarily driven by money, as this would lead to false incentives.³⁵

Secondly, a number of incentives are offered at **company level**. The insights gained by PEXs into the working methods and education and training activities of other companies are immediately beneficial for identifying potential for optimisation in their own work and in their own company. Companies can also use the PEX role as a form of professional enrichment for their employees, as PEX tasks are interesting, challenging and linked to specific further education and training opportunities. This company recognition can help to increase employees' intrinsic motivation and performance, which in turn benefits the company.

Thirdly, a number of incentives are offered at **system level**. PEXs are valued and recognised for their contribution to the smooth functioning of the VET system and for their commitment to training a new generation of qualified professionals in the VET landscape. They are actively involved in decision-making processes and development activities within the VET system, allowing them to contribute their experience and expertise and help shape the future of VET.

Despite these diverse incentives, the data analysed suggests that a PEX shortage could emerge in the future (see Figure 15). While only a few professional organisations report no current recruitment difficulties, the majority report a shortage of PEXs in certain professions or state that the search for PEXs has generally become more challenging. It must be assumed that around a third of the professional organisations are even experiencing an acute shortage of PEXs.³⁵

PEX shortage on the horizon

If there are not enough PEXs available for the annual QPs, there is a risk that the final exams will not be able to be conducted objectively, economically or fairly. This section highlights three particularly relevant factors that can affect the availability of PEXs: demographics, revision of occupations and cost-benefit considerations. Firstly, demographic aspects play an important role. The age distribution of PEXs and the situation on the skilled labour market in the industry are particularly significant reasons for shortages. If many older PEXs are active in an industry, a considerable number of them leave each year due to retirement and the associated term limits. Equally, if there is a general shortage of qualified specialists and young professionals in the industry, there will also be fewer potential new PEXs, which may lead to a gap in the PEX pool. In growing

Figure 15: Categories of PEX availability with examples of professional organisation (figures from October 2023)

Source: 360-degree interviews with relevant VET stakeholders.³⁵

professional fields in which new apprenticeships are being created, it is important to build up PEX capacities at the same time so that the increasing number of final exams can be managed.⁸¹

A second factor impacting the number of PEXs takes the form of revision of occupations. When new examination regulations increase the requirements for conducting QPs, and for PEXs by extension, this can lead to many PEXs stepping down all at once. Some may not wish to learn the new requirements and/or use the revision as an opportunity for a career change. Furthermore, adjustments decided upon during the revision of QP requirements can increase the demand for PEXs and consequently trigger a shortage.

Thirdly, cost-benefit considerations can lead to traditional normative divisions of tasks and costs being called into question. In the spirit of the militia concept, the financial compensation of the PEXs often cannot compete with regular salaries. Although this issue has been discussed at length in the circles concerned,³⁵ only minor changes are recognisable at this level.

In addition to financial compensation, time off from work granted by the companies is an important factor.

Traditionally, companies have often released their employees from work for PEX duties so that the role could be performed during working hours, sometimes even with additional compensation. Professional organisations are now observing, however, that many PEXs fulfil their tasks in their free time, although the reasons for this are unclear.³⁵ It is possible that many companies are no longer willing to make working time available for PEXs due to increased cost pressure. Without support and recognition from employers, motivation for engaging in PEX duties outside of regular work hours tends to decrease. In some cases, especially young potential PEXs are not prepared to give up a significant proportion of their free time for what is typically only modest financial compensation.³⁵ This can lead to difficulties in recruiting PEXs and consequently to PEX shortages in the longer term.

Development prospects for the future of PEXs

Intensified association efforts: Recruitment strategies and company involvement

Professional organisations can help to partially mitigate the shortage of PEXs through clever recruitment strategies and targeted promotion of young talent. By integrating young professionals into the association structures at an early stage, for example, their professional identity is strengthened and their role as a PEX can be

properly recognised as part of the association's activities. In dialogue with their member companies, professional organisations can also discuss issues such as declining participation or a lack of release time for PEXs by companies⁷⁹ to develop mutually supported solutions specific to their profession and industry. Modelled on VET funds aimed at sustaining corporate training efforts, it would also be conceivable to establish a similar cantonal or industry-specific initiative to support companies that facilitate militia activities by providing the necessary time off.

Addressing increased demands on PEXs: Further education and training programmes and their recognition

To meet the increasing demands on PEXs, it would be beneficial to develop additional accessible and attractive further education and training programmes. Short learning modules could be provided through a nationwide digital platform for PEXs such as the one Germany has had since 2023 with Leando.⁸² This would not only enable PEXs to access all relevant information about the PEX role from a central hub, but also to benefit from specific, job-related learning opportunities. At the same time, a digital platform would offer attractive networking opportunities that could help to strengthen the PEX community. Greater recognition could be achieved if PEX education and training and militia work were generally recognised as creditable achievements for formal education and further education and training programmes.

Lightening the load for PEXs: Examination design and digitalisation

The revision procedures in the VET Ordinance provide opportunities to reconsider examination concepts, taking into account the needs and workloads of PEXs. There may also be opportunities to reduce the workload of PEXs through clear, user-friendly processes and QP assessment grids, which are increasingly available digitally – for example, via the web-based application 'PkOrg' that offers software for examination board organisation. Digital tools and AI applications are likely to reduce the workload of PEXs further still in the future (see chapter 5). Digitally structured QPs could be particularly motivating for young PEXs, as in many cases this is reflective of their digitalised everyday lives. Nevertheless, comprehensive digitalisation of QPs would generate additional education and training requirements for PEXs, so it would be important to develop digital examination tools suitable for various professions so that the digitalisation of QPs is also worthwhile for professions with fewer learners and resources.

PEXs as the heart of practice-oriented QPs

The commitment of PEXs is crucial for implementing QPs in terms of ensuring practical and labour market relevance; however, like other areas of the militia system, this commitment is under pressure from societal and economic changes. To ensure continuity, affiliated partners must come together to develop solutions, including measures to boost the recognition of PEXs and ensure the role remains appealing – especially for the younger generation. In principle, it would be conceivable to professionalise PEX activities or increase state regulation. However, in the interests of a jointly supported VET system, it would be preferable for affiliated partners to cooperate and develop solutions to these challenges, taking into account the latest research and practical insights while continuing to pursue existing efforts.^{83, 84}

7 DISCUSSION: CHALLENGES AND FIELDS OF ACTION

This report has focused on the qualification procedures (QP) in vocational education and training (VET), seeking to address the challenges currently facing QPs and identify scope for improvement. The complexity of QPs in VET is higher than in usual school-leaving examinations, for example, as the focus is not on testing specialised knowledge but on practical competences. Furthermore, QPs are occupation-specific, sometimes company-specific, and subject to rapid change due to technological advancements. After all, QPs should be designed to reflect developments in the world of work and VET.

To fulfil this requirement, QPs must be continuously adapted to current circumstances. In this context, this trend report has identified several social, educational, societal and technological challenges and outlined starting points for possible solutions. This final section aims to discuss six action-relevant topics and findings to promote the further development of QPs.

1. There is currently an intensive debate in VET as to whether all QP elements in their current form meet the requirements of a competence-based examination.

At the heart of this discussion is the question of whether written final exams in professional knowledge and general education can be dispensed with, since the combination of the other QP modules is sufficient, and since written exams do not tend to align with a competence-based approach. The decisive question is therefore whether it would still be possible to test the relevant knowledge and competences in sufficient breadth and depth without final exams.

In principle, the flexible combination options of the QP modules allow the examination elements and formats to be specifically adapted to the respective professional context. Nevertheless, further research is needed to analyse the QP results for each occupation before and after changes to the QP structure, and to show the extent to which changes such as the elimination of written exams can impact success rates, long-term employment and educational pathways. This analysis has shown that while a relatively large number of learners receive unsatisfactory grades in professional knowledge, they are

often able to compensate for this with a strong performance in other areas. Regardless of the specific QP structure, it is also essential for learners to be well prepared, which requires high-quality education and training as well as effective cooperation across learning locations.

→ Whether written final exams or other QP components can be effectively replaced requires in-depth investigation across individual professions. It is crucial here that the selected combination of QP modules and the way they are implemented result in a high level of examination quality in line with the quality criteria for good examinations.

2. The choice of an individual practical project or pre-assigned examination project has a notable impact on overall QP success, as its status as a mandatory pass component leads relatively often to QP failure.

The individual practical project (IPP) or the pre-assigned (PEP) examination project is crucial to QP success, as it is designated as a mandatory pass component in most occupations so that learners have to achieve a sufficient grade in order to pass the QPs. Nevertheless, the proportion of unsatisfactory grades for learners undertaking a PEP is on average around three times higher than for those who chose an IPP, although there are considerable differences between occupations. The decision in favour of choosing an IPP or a PEP is often based on specific professional requirements. However, the available results indicate that a PEP is more challenging for learners, as it does not involve any company-specific elements or the presence of a supervisor from within the company, thereby failing to reflect the familiar workplace setting. The outcome of a PEP therefore depends more on how well it corresponds to the learner's professional experience: for example, were the learners able to practise the task in question frequently, or did the company use the specialist terminology required for the examination? In contrast, an IPP is tailored more precisely to the learner's experience gained within the training company. Nevertheless, the more individualised nature of the

IPP also means that the examination content and results are less comparable and therefore less objective. In addition to the fundamental question of 'IPP or PEP?', it therefore makes sense to specifically review the quality of both examination formats. The PEP should ensure that learners are not favoured or disadvantaged due to their different company backgrounds. It may be possible to compensate for differences in professional practices in the tasks set and by the examination experts (PEXs) without significantly weakening the standardised assessment of the necessary professional competences. With IPPs, on the other hand, it is essential to evaluate whether they are sufficiently standardised to allow learners to demonstrate their vocational aptitude objectively and validly in combination with the other QP modules.

→ As the IPP and the PEP are standardised differently and have different pass rates, the choice of the respective format and its structure should be reviewed in terms of validity, fairness and objectivity.

3. There are clear differences in the success rate between occupations and cantons and according to the individual characteristics of the learners, particularly on the first QP attempt. There are also indications that the quality of company training plays an important role.

The high failure rates in some occupations are stressful for learners, raise questions about fairness, and jeopardise the image of occupations. The findings indicate that the risk factors for QP failures are cumulative in some occupations. Academically weaker learners requiring additional support often find themselves in companies that are under significant production pressure^{24, 25} and offer a below-average quality of education and training as a result. A considerable portion of these occupations also have to contend with above-average dropout rates.

In addition to the need for early detection of potential issues on the part of learners and/or companies, this indicates that there is an alignment issue in certain occupations, in that the companies do not always find the learners they need or else the learners do not (or cannot) take up the occupation that suits them well. In the dual-track system, where learners decide for themselves which positions to apply for and companies select which learners to take on based on the applications they receive, potential alignment issues are somewhat inherent in the system, although these can be mitigated.

→ In occupations with high failure rates and frequent reorientations, there is a real need to improve the alignment between companies and learners. Furthermore, learners and companies should be (even) better supported in recognising problems at an early stage and addressing them during education and training.

4. Around 10 per cent of learners do not take the QPs within five years of starting their VET programme and achieve an upper secondary level (Sec II) leaving certificate with either a considerable delay or never at all.

If results are taken into account, 99 per cent of learners who take their examinations successfully complete the QP. A one-off failure in the QP is therefore not a major cause of a missing Sec II leaving certificate. Given that a certain level of failure is to be expected if only those with the necessary competences for professional practice are to pass, VET demonstrates excellent QP success rates.

Nevertheless, the significant proportion of learners who do not even attempt the QP at all and so remain without a post-compulsory education certificate for the time being is problematic. This group should be (even) better supported in achieving Sec II leaving certificate, yet they are often difficult to reach, since many of them have already left the education system. Various initiatives exist at cantonal level to guide young adults towards a professional qualification, including longer education and training obligations or specific support for young adults without professional qualifications.⁸⁵⁻⁸⁷

→ When assessing the overall success of the QP, particular attention should be paid to the group of learners who do not even attempt the QP. Targeted support measures should be (further) developed for this group.

5. The use of electronic qualification procedures (eQP) and artificial intelligence (AI) expands the possibilities for structuring the QPs and has already sparked several innovative processes in the design and implementation of examination elements in many – particularly technology-driven – professional fields.

Technological advancements have the potential to make QPs more realistic, cost-effective and inclusive. How-

ever, questions arise regarding the implementation of competence-based assessments, access to suitable hardware and software, misuse of AI, and data security. VET is particularly affected by trends in digitalisation and AI, as the increasing use of digital work methods and AI programs in vocational and educational practices should be reflected in competence-based performance assessments in QPs.

When using digital aids and AI in QPs, the main question is whether they adequately reflect the reality of teaching and work. For instance, if digital tools have the potential to enhance the validity of assessments for an occupation, a case should be made for them to be used.

- The use of new technologies in QPs should be specifically tailored to the requirements of individual professions and QP modules. Rapid technological progress is leading to an increased need for further education and training, opportunities for exchange, and guidance for all those involved in QPs.

6. Those involved in VET are faced with the challenge of attracting and retaining enough qualified and committed professionals for PEX activities.

This is partly due to the increased demands on PEXs, the more difficult recruitment process and the partially weakening incentive system. While some industries and professions succeed in positioning the roles of PEXs to create added value for individuals, businesses, and the VET system, other professions require further efforts. Targeted association work can help to promote the involvement of businesses and young professionals in militia activities. Addressing the increased demands could be achieved through accessible further education and training and learning opportunities, as well as through a central platform for information, learning and exchange. Digital tools and streamlined exam administration could also contribute to relieving the burden on PEXs.

In principle, it would be possible to professionalise PEX activities or increase state regulation. Nonetheless, in the interests of a jointly supported VET system, it would be preferable for affiliated partners to cooperate and develop solutions to these challenges.

- More attention should be paid at national level to the issue of securing the PEX pool in the long term. The development of joint solutions by affiliated partners to recognise and strengthen PEX work is particularly important in this regard.

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REMARKS

- i The elements professional knowledge and performance grade are rarely designed as mandatory pass components; in exceptional cases, they are combined into a single mandatory pass component and the average grade across the two is counted. The 2011 VET Ordinance outlines a slightly different approach to mandatory pass components for the profession of the commercial employee FVD, which includes regulating the pass criteria at the subordinate level of the subject grade.
- ii In addition to the five key quality criteria of validity, reliability, objectivity, economy and fairness, the literature also refers to other criteria such as scaling, standardisation, comparability, usefulness, reasonableness and integrity.^{12,13} There are also other quality markers of good examinations, although these tend to serve more as recommendations for examinations in VET. These notably include organisation, time management, and preparation and follow-up (cf. the SFUVET PEX handbook⁹, section 4.1.3, for example).
- iii This refers to equal examination conditions for all learners, and can also encompass broader aspects, such as aligning exam conditions with both workplace and school learning environments.¹⁶
- iv The pass rate rose in the first year of the pandemic from an average of around 93 per cent to just over 95 per cent (Figure 6), which is likely to be primarily due to the suspension of written examinations for the professional knowledge and general education. In 2020, the results of the written examinations were calculated based on the performance grades and the special project.¹⁹
- v The multivariate and descriptive analyses also included the parents' educational background. No significant influence of educational background can be identified in the multivariate models.
- vi See Article 45 paragraph 2 of the Vocational Training Act, Articles 44 and 45 of the VET Ordinance and the respective ordinance on VET (qualified specialist training, appropriate pedagogical and methodological/didactic skills, FVD for the professional field or equivalent qualification, qualifying further training, several years of professional experience in company-based training).

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial intelligence
FSO	Swiss Federal Statistical Office
eQP	Electronic qualification procedure
FVB	Swiss Federal Vocational Baccalaureate (Berufsmaturität)
FVB 1	Swiss Federal Vocational Baccalaureate parallel to the three- or four-year VET programme leading to a FVD
FVC	Swiss Federal VET Certificate; awarded on completion of a two-year VET programme
FVD	Swiss Federal VET Diploma; awarded on completion of a three- or four-year VET programme
IGKG Schweiz	Swiss interest group for basic commercial training
IPP	Individual practical project – one of the formats of the practical project QP element
LABB	Longitudinal analyses in the education sector
NEET	Not in education, employment or training
PACT	Premature apprenticeship contract termination
PEP	Pre-assigned examination project – one of the formats of the practical project QP element
PEX	Examination expert
QP	Qualification procedures
Sec I/II	Secondary level I/II
VET	Vocational education and training

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